

induced by UV-B radiation was the result of UV-dependent destruction of IAA and the formation of growth-inhibiting IAA photoproducts. Similarly, the growth response of rice plants to elevated UV-B radiation may be associated with the changes in endogenous concentrations of IAA and ABA in UV-B treated plants.

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Risk analysis of rice leaf blast epidemics associated with effects of enhanced ultra-violet-B and temperature changes in the Philippines

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Climatic variation and pests, of which rice blast is among the most important, greatly influence rice production in the tropics. The risk of blast epidemics caused by global climate changes is important to consider when developing disease control strategies. Previous work at IRRI has shown that lower temperatures in the tropics promote severe blast and highest yield loss and that elevated UV-B radiation causes more lesions, faster lesion expansion, and reduced spore viability. UV-B effects on rice growth and blast are therefore available for integrating into models to simulate blast epidemics and rice yield.

The objectives of this study were to incorporate UV-B effects into the RICE-BLAST model, and to simulate blast epidemics in the Philippines under a range of temperatures combined with elevated UV-B effects. Risk assessment was based on simulation results.

Model modification. A combination model, RICE-BLAST, was developed from the CERES-RICE model coupled to the BLASTSIM model and used to simulate rice blast epidemics based on rice growth and blast infection on leaves. Relative ratios of lesion number, lesion area expansion rate, and sporulation rate under UV-B exposure were coupled into corresponding subroutines by changing corresponding rates in blast infection. New external data files containing ratios

of effects of UV-B on components were developed. Variety IR30 was simulated under nonlimited water and nitrogen conditions. Estimated weather data under a normal year in Solana, Philippines, were used to simulate rice growth in the first growing season (Jan-May). UV-B effects on rice growth were quantified as a) reduction of net assimilation rate (decrease of dry weight and growth rate of leaf, stem, root, and grain caused by UV-B are the results from this reduction) and b) growth rate reduction for each component, such as reduction of dry weight accumulation rate of leaf, stem, root, and grain.

Two different coupling approaches using four components—leaf area, leaf, stem, and root dry weight—were tested: single coupling, in which only assimilation rate was considered, and multiple coupling, in which components including growth rates of root, leaf, and stem, were considered. We determined that single coupling is better than multiple coupling to simulate UV-B effects on rice growth; UV-B effects on leaf area predicted by multiple coupling is greater than that of observations; single coupling routine is to make the model more explanatory of the effects of UV-B on rice growth; and it is reasonable to use the modified model to simulate blast epidemics occurring under UV-B effects.

Parameter estimation. The relative ratios of UV-R treatments compared with controls were calculated from growth and physiological parameters of rice varieties IR30 and IR74 as affected by 4 wk of UV-B treatment (Q. Daj, IRRI, unpubl. data) and from the effects of UV-B on blast lesion number and lesion size under enhanced UV-B treatment and control on two UV-B-sensitive varieties, IR30 and IR72, infected with blast isolate PO6-6 (Finckh 1993).

Lesion expansion rate was estimated by $r = 1/t \cdot \log(L2/L1)$, where r is lesion expansion rate; $L1$ and $L2$ are lesion sizes, in mm^2 , at beginning date of lesion appearance and observation date, respectively; and t is number of days between date of lesion appearance and observation. $L1$ is assumed to be 5 mm^2 and t is 5 d. $L2$ was obtained from experimental data.

Relative ratio of lesion expansion (RRL) can be calculated from $RRL = rt/rc$, where R is lesion expansion rate under UV-B treatment and rc is lesion expansion rate under no UV-B control. Effect of UV-B on lesion number can be considered as similar to its effect on infection efficiency. Relative ratio of infection efficiency for the two varieties was calculated by lesion number under UV-B treatment divided by that of no UV-B control. Data of UV-B effect on sporulation were from unpublished data (Leung, Washington State University).

Simulation of global change effects. Thirty years of estimated weather data from seven Philippine locations, produced using either of two programs—WGEN or WMARK—were used in the simulations. Global temperature change treatments were considered by changing the estimated daily temperature data by +3, +1, 0, -1, and -3 °C. Three growing seasons for each location were separately simulated. In each growing season of each simulation year under each temperature change level, four situations were simulated: no blast without UV-B, blast without UV-R, no blast with UV-B, and blast with UV-B. Estimated yield, simulated area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC), and maximum severity of blast were produced at the end of each simulation run. AUDPC and maximum severity caused by blast without UV-B were compared with that caused by blast with UV-B effects. A risk scenario

was produced for each condition of temperature change using GIs.

Simulations of global change effects in the Philippines. Simulation results from each of 7 locations, on yield and disease, were analyzed for each temperature condition interacting with a UV-B treatment. Means and standard deviations were calculated for comparison in different temperature change and UV-B treatments. Results are summarized as follows:

- The yield loss caused by UV-B was normally at 9-10%, independent of temperature change, and its deviation is much smaller than that caused by blast.
- Enhanced UV-B will cause more severe blast epidemics compared with situations without UV-B. In most cases of temperature changes, except -3°C, maximum disease severity and AUDPC were doubled or more under UV-B effect.
- UV-B will cause much more severe blast when the temperature change is -3°C compared with other temperature change levels.
- In most cases, yield loss caused by blast with UV-B is greater than the sum of individual losses caused by blast and enhanced UV-B.
- Yield loss caused by blast with UV-B is generally at 15-20% under most temperature change conditions, except -3°C.

In this study, RICE-BLAST model was modified by incorporating enhanced UV-B effects into the individual rice and blast models, using IR30. To further test the model, parameters and complete experimental data from more varieties are needed as are independent data of blast epidemics occurring under enhanced UV-B. These kinds of data, however, are difficult to obtain from field experiments; until they can be, predictions of global change effects on blast must remain tentative.

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Research methodology

How to adjust grain yield to 14% moisture content

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Grain yield of rice is usually reported based on 14% moisture content. This allows comparison of yields across locations and years. Grain moisture content of 14%, however, may be expressed on a fresh weight (fw) or dry weight (dw) basis. Moisture content on a fw basis (MC_{fw}) is generally higher than moisture content based on dw (MC_{dw}). This difference becomes greater as MC increases.

Moisture percentage on a fw basis ($\% MC_{fw}$) and dw basis ($\% MC_{dw}$) can be converted from one to the other using the following equations:

$$\% MC_{fw} = 100 \times \% MC_{dw} / (100 + \% MC_{dw}) \quad (1)$$

$$\% MC_{dw} = 100 \times \% MC_{fw} / (100 - \% MC_{fw}) \quad (2)$$

Electric moisture meters are commonly used to determine grain moisture content. These meters generally measure the conductivity or capacitance of seeds and express the moisture content as $\% MC_{fw}$, not $\% MC_{dw}$. The correct equation to use in calculating the grain yield adjusted to 14% MC, is

$$\text{Adjusted weight (14\% } MC_{fw}) = W \times (1 - 0.01 \times \% MC_{fw}) / 0.86 \quad (3)$$

where W is the weight of the grains and $\% MC_{fw}$ is the moisture meter reading. On the other hand, the equation for calculating grain yield adjusted to 14% MC_{dw} is

$$\text{Adjusted weight (14\% } MC_{dw}) = W \times (1 - 0.01 \times \% MC_{fw}) \times 1.14 \quad (4)$$

The adjusted grain weight calculated with equation 3 is nearly 2% higher than that with equation 4, meaning that the grain yield adjusted to 14% MC_{dw} is almost 2% lower than grain yield

adjusted to 14% MC_{fw} . Therefore, when reporting grain yield, indicate whether the 14% MC is expressed on a dw or fw basis. It is preferable to report grain yield adjusted to 14% MC based on fw using equation 3. ■

A new method for transporting *Azolla* culture collections

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Azolla is a free-floating water fern that fixes atmospheric N_2 in association with N_2 -fixing cyanobacterium *Anabaena azollae* that can be used in wetland ricefields.

The survival of *Azolla* is poor, however, when it is removed from water, making transport difficult. Scientists doing *Azolla* research transport culture collections in tissue paper soaked with N free nutrient solution in plastic petri dishes. This method is not ideal because the moist tissue paper is conducive to rotting the plants, causing the fronds to die. To overcome this problem, we carried out a laboratory experiment to assess the survival of *Azolla* fronds stored in polythene bags.

Fresh fronds of *A. microphylla* and *A. filiculoides* were collected from culture tanks and washed repeatedly in tap water and then in distilled water. Fronds were placed in tissue paper and gently pressed for 30 min to remove adhering moisture. Ten grams of fronds were packed tightly into polythene bags, which were then sealed or stapled. Two sets were stored in the laboratory for 6 wk at $27 \pm 1^\circ C$ in light at 3000 lux intensity and in the dark. More than 70% of the fronds of the species survived and could be revived in N-free liquid medium. The study was repeated three times with the same results.

This easy method is recommended for transporting *Azolla* cultures. ■